

ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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THE CONCEPT OF LEGALIZATION OF PROCEEDS FROM CRIME AND FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO THEIR RECEIPT

ANNOTATION

This article discusses issues related to the emergence of the phenomenon of legalization of proceeds from crime. The article examines the evolution of the term “legalization (laundering) of proceeds from crime” in international legal acts. The socio-economic prerequisites for the emergence of money laundering are also considered.

Key words: legalization of income, money laundering, anti-money laundering, law, regulations.

ЖИНОЯТДАН ОЛИНГАН ДАРОМАДЛАРНИ ЛЕГАЛЛАШТИРИШ ТУШУНЧАСИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ОЛИНИШИГА ЁРДАМ БЕРУВЧИ ОМИЛЛАР

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада жиноятдан олинган даромадларни легаллаштириш феноменининг пайдо бўлиши билан боғлиқ масалалар муҳокама қилинган. Мақолада халқаро ҳуқуқий ҳужжатларда «жиноятдан олинган даромадларни легаллаштириш» атамасининг эволюцияси кўриб чиқилган. Жиноий даромадларни легаллаштиришнинг пайдо бўлишининг ижтимоий-иқтисодий шартлари ҳам кўриб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: даромадларни легаллаштириш, ноқонуний даромадларни яшириш, ноқонуний даромадларни легаллаштиришга қарши курашиш, қонун, қоидалар.

ПОНЯТИЕ ЛЕГАЛИЗАЦИИ ДОХОДОВ, ПОЛУЧЕННЫХ ПРЕСТУПНЫМ ПУТЕМ, И ФАКТОРЫ, СПОСОБСТВУЮЩИЕ ИХ ПОЛУЧЕНИЮ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы, связанные с возникновением явления легализации доходов, полученных преступным путем. В статье рассматривается эволюция термина «легализация (отмывание) доходов, полученных преступным путем» в международных правовых актах. Также рассмотрены социально-экономические предпосылки возникновения легализации преступных доходов.

Ключевые слова: легализация доходов, отмывание доходов, противодействие отмыванию доходов, право, нормативные документы.

Legalization (laundering) of proceeds from crime makes it possible to hide illegal sources of profit and thus turns illegal activities into a highly profitable type of business [1].

Money laundering refers to the process of converting illegally obtained money into legal money. Many definitions of this concept have been proposed. “Money laundering is the process by which the existence, illicit origin or illicit use of proceeds is concealed and then these proceeds are disguised so as to appear to be of legitimate origin”.

Legalization (laundering) of proceeds from crime is the final stage of transforming crime into a highly profitable and effective type of illegal business. Once the layering process has been successfully completed, the money launderer must create an appearance of credibility when explaining the sources of his wealth.

The issue of money laundering, which means the legalization of proceeds obtained by criminal or illegal means, has become particularly acute in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Without resolving this issue, it is impossible to continue economic reforms in the country. The most serious concern is the extent to which money laundering has become and the damage this practice causes to the economy and society.

Banks act as gatekeepers of the legitimate financial system. Only their vigilance can protect the system from organized criminal groups, corrupt officials and terrorists, without giving them a tool for concealing proceeds from criminal activities. Banks play a critical role in preventing and detecting money laundering and reporting it to the relevant authorities.

It is based on the principle of priority use of the banking structure for the purpose of combating money laundering. FATF experts proceed from the fact that it is the banking system, especially in the era of globalization of financial services, that is most exposed to the risks associated with money laundering [2].

According to Art. 3 of the Convention, legalization (“laundering”) of proceeds from crime means:

- conversion or transfer of property, knowing that such property was obtained as a result of an offense or offenses, or as a result of participation in such an offense or offenses, for the purpose of concealing or disguising the illicit source of the property or for the purpose of assisting any person participating in the commission of such an offense or offenses so that it can evade responsibility for its actions;

- concealment or concealment of the true nature, source, location, method of disposal, movement, true rights in relation to property or its belongings, if it is known that such property was obtained as a result of offenses or offenses, as a result of participation in such an offense or offenses;

- acquisition, possession or use of property, if at the time of its receipt it was known that such property was obtained as a result of an offense or offenses or as a result of participation in such an offense or offenses;

- participation, complicity or entering into a criminal conspiracy to commit any offense or offenses listed above, an attempt to commit such an offense or offenses, as well as aiding, abetting, assisting or consulting in their commission” [3].

The UN Vienna Convention has recognized the “laundering” of money received from drug trafficking as a crime. At the same time, the development of organized crime has led to an increase in the income of criminal organizations received from other areas of criminal activity. Part of this income also began to be laundered and invested in the legal economy.

A criminal laundering proceeds is faced with the following task: to take all measures to ensure that an outsider does not find out where the money came from and with the help of whom it was distributed to certain institutions or organizations. In order to accomplish this task, they usually carry out the following activities:

- use of banks to open accounts, located, as a rule, far from the place of work and residence of criminals;
- transfer of money to the country of residence from abroad, but legally from new accounts of companies or other institutions;
- use of an underground system of bank accounts.

Methods by which criminals exploit traditional financial institutions include:

- smurfing – turning cash into financial instruments;
- exchange of small banknotes for larger denominations;
- exchange transactions - an organized exchange of money for banknotes of a different denomination or other currency;
- structuring cash transactions;
- establishing control over financial institutions;
- illegal use of exceptions to the law;
- use of correspondent relationships between banks;
- creating a false paper trail;
- merger of legal and illegal funds;
- transfer of criminally obtained money abroad;
- use of “collective” accounts;
- use of transit accounts;
- loan guarantee mechanism [4];

Let's look at some of the placement methods in more detail.

Structuring and other money laundering techniques may be transferred to non-traditional financial institutions. A method of merging legal and illegal funds that will be discussed when analyzing the role of non-traditional financial institutions in money laundering.

Placement through non-traditional financial institutions:

Non-traditional financial institutions are those that actually provide banking services. These include currency exchanges, securities or precious metals brokers, commodity brokers, casinos, organizations providing telegraph and postal services and services for exchanging checks for cash.

Non-bank financial institutions can be used for money laundering in the same ways as traditional financial institutions, particularly by structuring, subordinating and merging funds.

Recently, these financial organizations have become increasingly used to launder illegally obtained proceeds and introduce them into regular financial circulation. This is largely due to the fact that in the banking sector legislation aimed at combating capital laundering is more developed and more effective.

In some cases, entrepreneurs themselves become active members of political groups or close associates of political leaders. Both the new business class and the lobbying politicians have the same interest - to enrich themselves at the expense of the country.

Political leaders holding important positions in government administration often provide privileged business groups with monopoly protection and even economic espionage services, and in return receive generous bribes from them [5].

Legalization is a process through which criminally obtained proceeds are poured into legal money circulation, while the real sources and channels of receipt of such income (money) are carefully hidden from prying attention.

Money laundering is carried out by organized criminal structures, the purpose of which is both to further finance criminal activities and to obtain the opportunity to use illegally obtained funds for various purposes.

Real (illegal) sources of income in the process of obtaining and legalizing them in many cases can be hidden behind completely legal-looking activities, and can also coexist with them in parallel. Legalized “dirty” money is abstracted in the process of laundering from the source of its illegal origin and thus becomes part of the legal economy.

Money laundering is not limited to drug trafficking and terrorism, which involve large amounts of cash. Illegal trade in weapons, radioactive materials, organized crime, illegal financial activities, clandestine alcohol production, fraud, kidnapping, terrorism, theft of public funds and funds - all this and much more creates more than favorable conditions for the emergence of significant illegal capital.

The presence of such funds in the country is recognized by the international community as a sufficient condition for large-scale criminal financial transactions [6].

Against this background, the number of identified cases of legalization (laundering) of funds or other property acquired by criminal means is also increasing. According to UN experts, the annual turnover of organized crime is about 500 billion dollars, half of which is funds received from drug trafficking [7].

Such amounts are laundered annually by criminal economic structures. The latest research notes the connection of this process with the characteristics of the economy, and “laundering” is considered as one of the main activities of organized crime.

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